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The Purpose and Content of Teaching Reading English

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***Annotation:** This scientific article is devoted to the purpose and content of teaching English reading. Also, it informs about methods of teaching English.*

***Key words:** Comprehension, fluency, vocabulary, critical thinking, engagement.*

INTRODUCTION

Globalism is rapidly developing, and in this context, it is crucial to implement effective methods and approaches for reforms in the education system. New Uzbekistan is taking steps to assimilate the most suitable options from global science and to establish a national methodological foundation.

In recent years, attention has been focused on developing systematic concepts that provide clear solutions to problems. A specific mechanism has been outlined within the framework of the "Action Strategy" to enhance the effectiveness of education.

The systematic and strategic methods of teaching English from the basic to the advanced levels have become one of the pressing issues of our time. Since the early years of independence, advancements in educational methodology have enabled effective use of advanced educational technologies from around the world. This process is vital for aligning education with modern requirements and achieving long-term goals. Based on the decree on "Measures to Elevate the Activities for Promoting Foreign Language Learning in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a Qualitatively New Level," a comprehensive system has been introduced for learning, teaching, and widely implementing foreign languages, specifically addressing existing issues in basic education. As a practical result, the in-depth, clear, optimal, and targeted approach to teaching English in primary grades after preschool education reinforces our previous considerations. It is important to note that extensive attention is being given to "implementing international educational standards and enhancing the quality and effectiveness of higher education institutions based on quality assessment," creating conditions for primary school students to demonstrate effective assimilation competencies.

Thus, the goals and objectives set before us are fundamentally focused on developing the child's personal intellect, the growth and changes in their consciousness and emotions, and timely addressing

the problems that arise, which is one of the significant areas of research. It is no secret that the education system today differs significantly from yesterday, and the process of its implementation is also evolving. The systematic organization of this process necessitates addressing the pressing issues related to overcoming dyslexia.

METHODS

Considering the adaptability of young adolescents to family and school environments, the dyslexia problem is naturally shifting towards a solution.

Dyslexia refers to a specific learning difficulty that affects a person's ability to read, write, and spell, despite having normal intelligence. Addressing dyslexia requires theoretical and methodological explorations, especially regarding whether individuals with speech impairments can freely and accurately pronounce concepts and assimilations in foreign languages, given that they might struggle to pronounce their own native language correctly. These pressing questions undoubtedly concern every teacher and expert in the field, as the rapid passage of time and the need to acquire certain knowledge and skills have made finding optimal solutions a necessity.

Today's generation has sufficiently absorbed the conditions of the technological world, where a pragmatic approach dominates their worldview and perceptions. This includes mastering various smart mechanisms and engaging with nanotechnological tools. Consequently, there is an urgent need to address the proper pronunciation of speech and phonetic units, as well as letters, among the younger generation. In classrooms, not every student is able to pronounce letters, symbols, words, and sentences in English correctly. Additionally, the influence of the evolving technological landscape may lead to a sense of "silence" among them. This suggests that a child who is overwhelmed by various communication tools in the family environment may experience a decline in their ability to speak freely. Our research, which aims to properly educate students with pronunciation difficulties using games and similar effective tools, significantly contributes to enhancing their speaking skills.

In schools, especially in primary grades, the presence of congenital dyslexia in children can also arise from pathological conditions, fear, stress, and difficulties in adapting to life. Conflicts between parents in the family environment and surrounding conditions can naturally lead to such issues. From birth until adulthood, individuals have a continuous need for education and upbringing. Neglecting a child's proper nutrition, sleep, and adaptability can result in the emergence of weak and speech-related impairments.

Various types of this problem have been introduced into the educational systems of advanced methodological schools around the world. The mixing of diverse information from the environment, along with the failure to timely develop a child's ability to express certain thoughts and reflections freely, is one of the systemic phenomena that arises. By accurately identifying the scope of this issue and understanding a child's speech and cognitive growth in favorable conditions, it is possible to ensure that they can assimilate foreign languages as easily and comfortably as their native language.

Language teaching is always implemented in two ways:

1. Practical and comparative.
2. Theoretical.

RESULTS

In this aspect, systematic language teaching requires identifying the distinctive features of the English language compared to other languages, particularly in establishing a proper approach in primary

grades. The communicative approach segments allow for the emergence of various practical skills today. The etiquette of interaction between the teacher and the student, progressing from simplicity to complexity, and the comprehensive support for children with dyslexia contribute to enhancing the ability to work in small groups.

This process is reflected in various aspects of life, such as in communication on the streets, within families, among friends, and in both group and individual learning environments.

Children with dyslexia may possess deep knowledge, but they face several challenges in expressing it. The methodological theoretical concept of timely addressing these difficulties has aimed to prevent quite complex situations in Uzbekistan's education system over the past decade, and it demonstrates that a systematic and free approach to finding suitable solutions is being developed.

It is worth noting that "human activity is carried out in several forms: labor activity, cognitive activity, and speech (communication) activity, among others. Generally, psychology studies human activity and its psyche, while speech activity, as an intersecting field, is deeply explored in psycholinguistics. Psycholinguistics scientifically investigates the formation of inner speech in a person's speech activity and its connections with external activities. It is a complex and multifaceted task to study how knowledge and concepts about existence—philosophical and psychological characteristics—are conveyed to other members of society through speech.

The mechanism of speech formation, the physiological and acoustic processes involved, the selection and combination of words to form grammatical units, and the consideration of meaning are all essential aspects of this investigation. Furthermore, examining the characteristics of speech activity that relate to cognition and auditory perception is a primary task of psycholinguistic research.

DISCUSSION

Indeed, learning and teaching a language do not occur in isolation. Various related fields—such as natural sciences, history and literature, psychology, ethics and aesthetics, and logic—must be integrally connected to address this issue. Additionally, a teacher who correctly understands every aspect of life must first implement pragmatic approaches and be thoroughly informed about advanced technologies of the time.

This is especially evident in the necessity for foreign language teachers to be capable of considering life, contemporary developments, and the modern world that is advancing around them. For a person to think critically, they must also cultivate the ability to apply their full strength and potential effectively. The knowledge and skills of a teacher (in English language teaching) are defined not only by working with texts but also by their ability to analyze and interpret those texts and convey them to their students in a comfortable and useful manner.

Addressing the dyslexia of primary school students who are born with speech impairments is one of the significant tasks facing contemporary English language methodology. Moreover, foreign researchers like Yu. Kormos, R. Berlin, J. Nijakowska, E. Turner, and J. Pug have demonstrated that resolving speech issues is a process related to didactic education. In their studies, these scholars regard this issue as a crucial aspect of life and explain that its resolution depends on the teacher's ability to work deeply and systematically on their skills.

According to researcher N. Mustafaeva: "In our country, the issues of dysgraphia, dyslexia, and dyspraxia have become commonly regarded as medical and logopedic conditions. However, in our research, such speech problems, specifically those encountered during the process of learning a foreign language, are treated as the object of the teacher-pedagogue. If necessary, these issues are studied and

analyzed as a complex problem involving pedagogical collaboration, methods, and techniques used in the teaching process.

Indeed, in general education schools, the initial point of this problem is considered to arise from preschool and family education, making it optimal to start addressing it from basic education. In this process, a creative approach to education, creativity, and the effectiveness of educational methods aimed at finding convenient solutions to problems are emphasized. Particularly for English language teachers, it is essential not only to be providers of uniform education but also to systematically interpret individual teaching methodologies, which is defined by the application of modern standards. This principle justifies the confidence in recognizing the opportunities being created for teaching and learning foreign languages in our country as an integral aspect of understanding the realities of life."

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